

A1603

C2FUEL Solid Oxide Electrolyser Demonstration System

Timo Lehtinen, Matti Noponen

Elcogen, Niittyvillankuja 4, Vantaa 01510, Finland

Tel.: +358-50-546-1212

timo.lehtinen@elcogen.com

Abstract

The C2FUEL project aims to develop energy-efficient, economically and environmentally viable CO₂ conversion technologies. The project is focused to develop innovative production routes of dimethyl ether (DME) and formic acid (FA) from green hydrogen and industrial carbon dioxide. The C2FUEL concept will be demonstrated at Dunkirk industrial area.

This presentation outlines the current progress of the high temperature electrolysis demonstration system development for the C2FUEL project conducted by Elcogen. The electrolyser demonstration system is designed to deliver 1 Nm³/h of hydrogen at 40 bar. The electrolysis stack is Elcogen's own technology and it is operated at about 700°C. The processes for steam and gas supply, and heat management are implemented with standard industrial components. The gas pressurizing is conducted with a mechanical compressor which has an inherent feature to produce pressure variation on the suction side. Minimization of this pressure variation is conducted with system level solutions. Prior to the compression stage, hydrogen is dried in order to provide high quality hydrogen to the synthesis processes and to avoid water condensation in the pressurized components. The demonstrator is divided into two subsystems: electrolyser subsystem that produces hydrogen at atmospheric pressure and compressor subsystem which compresses the produced hydrogen to 40 bar. The subsystems are designed as separate modules and can be operated also freely from each other.

Introduction

Elcogen is one of the leading European manufacturers of solid oxide cell (SOC) technology. Elcogen products are unique combination of best-in-class performance and low-cost product structure. The unit cell and stack products are designed for low temperature operation enabling major cost reductions in the system level. Elcogen's operations are located in the Nordic-Baltic technology cluster of Finland and Estonia.

The main advantage of high temperature solid oxide electrolysis technology compared to low temperature electrolysis technologies, i.e., polymer electrolyte membrane and alkaline, is its higher electrical efficiency and thus reduced specific energy consumption. E.g., the specific energy consumption for a SOEC stack can be up to 25 - 45% lower than for PEMEC and AEC technologies and even on complete system level SOEC technology can provide 15 – 45 % better efficiencies [1].

Elcogen is a partner in the C2FUEL project which aims to develop energy-efficient, economically and environmentally viable CO₂ conversion technologies for the displacement of fossil fuel emission through a concept of industrial symbiosis between carbon intensive industries, power production, and local economy. The key technical and economic challenges to be tackled in the project are related to innovative production routes of dimethyl ether (DME) and formic acid (FA) from hydrogen (produced by Elcogen's technology) and captured carbon dioxide. The C2FUEL concept will be demonstrated at Dunkirk industrial area between DK6 combined cycle power plant, Arcelor Mittal steel factory and one of the major European harbours.

Elcogen's contribution to the C2FUEL project is to provide an electrolyser system that produces 1 Nm³/h of hydrogen at 40 bar for DME production. This presentation outlines the current progress of the high temperature electrolysis demonstrator development at Elcogen. The electrolysis stack is Elcogen's own technology and will be presented in the conference presentation A0503.

1. Electrolyser demonstration unit

The electrolyser demonstrator is designed to deliver 1 Nm³/h of hydrogen at 40 bar and dried to a dew point of -60 °C with reference to atmospheric pressure. The stack is operated at about 700 °C and at ambient pressure conditions. The processes for steam and gas supply, and heat management are implemented with standard industrial components. The stack is operated at ambient pressure conditions in order to minimize gas leakages in the stack and thus maximizing its lifetime. The gas pressurizing is conducted with a mechanical compressor which has an inherent feature to produce pressure variation on the suction side. Minimization of this pressure variation is conducted with system level solutions. Prior to the compression stage, hydrogen is dried in order to provide high quality hydrogen to the synthesis processes and to avoid water condensation in the pressurized components. The demonstrator is divided into two subsystems: electrolyser subsystem that produces atmospheric pressure hydrogen and compressor subsystem which compresses the produced hydrogen to 40 bar. The subsystems are designed modular and can be operated also freely from each other. The subsystems are installed in two standard 20 feet shipping containers. A simplified P&I diagram is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Simplified P&I-diagram of the electrolyser demonstrator

Electrolyser Subsystem

During the start-up, hydrogen and nitrogen are fed to the fuel electrode to maintain a reducing atmosphere at the fuel electrode. Air is fed to the air electrode to heat the stack evenly and balance pressure difference between the electrodes. Gases are heated with heat exchangers before the furnace and radiative heat exchangers within the furnace. The system is designed to utilize tap water for the electrolysis process. Water is cleaned to Type I ultrapure water within the system. During the electrolysis process, 10 mol-% of hydrogen is mixed with steam to protect the inlet side of the fuel electrode from oxidation. When the system is fully operational, hydrogen source is switched from bottled hydrogen to compressor outlet to reduce hydrogen consumption. Produced hydrogen exiting the electrolyser stack is cooled down with a condenser to remove most of the remaining water. Further drying is accomplished with a refrigerant dryer which reduces the dew point to 2 °C. Hydrogen exiting the electrolyser subsystem is at container temperature and atmospheric pressure. Design of the electrolyser subsystem is illustrated in Figure 4

Figure 4. Design of the electrolyser subsystem

Major components of the electrolyser subsystem such as furnace, heat exchangers, evaporator and drying equipment are installed in a closed frame which has a local ventilation with gas detection system. In case there is a hydrogen leakage, electricity is cut off from the components within the frame. Pipes leading to and leaving the electrolyser frame are continuous so leakages outside the frame are not possible, however, additional gas detectors are installed inside the container space to monitor gas leakages. Auxiliary equipment such as water treatment, air compressor and water cooling are installed in the container space. Automation cabinet is installed on the inside wall next to container doors and electrical cabinet on the outside, in a recess on the container wall.

All components have been installed in the container and electrical work has been started. Current plan is to finalize the container in May 2022 and start testing in June 2022. Assembly status of the electrolyser subsystem is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Assembly status of the electrolyser subsystem

Compressor Subsystem

Due to the reciprocating movement of the compressor, pressure at the inlet varies which is minimized with an inlet buffer tank. Hydrogen entering the subsystem is compressed to approximately 4 bar pressure with the first stage of the hydrogen compressor. A desiccant dryer between the compressor stages dries hydrogen to a dew point of $-60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with reference to atmospheric pressure. After drying, second stage of the compressor increases pressure to 40 bar. A recycle valve between inlet and outlet of the compressor maintains a constant flow through the compressor when hydrogen flow at the inlet of the subsystem varies due to the operation point of the electrolyser subsystem. The recycle valve ensures a constant pressure at the inlet of the compressor. Compressed hydrogen is led to the DME production and part of the hydrogen can be recycled back to the electrolyser subsystem to be mixed with steam for fuel electrode protection. Design of the compressor subsystem is illustrated in Figure 6.

Compressor and desiccant dryer are installed on the floor of the container whereas recycle valve, buffer tank and other components are installed on the wall. Similar to the electrolyser subsystem the automation cabinet is installed on the inside wall next to container doors and electrical cabinet on the outside, in a recess on the container wall.

Assembly of the compressor subsystem was finalized in January 2022 and container was transported to VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland in February 2022 in order to free assembly space for the electrolyser subsystem. Testing of the compressor subsystem is proceeding in parallel with the assembly of the electrolyser subsystem. A picture of finalized compressor subsystem is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 6. Design of the compressor subsystem

Figure 7. Finalized compressor subsystem

2. Summary

Elcogen stack can be used in electrolysis mode up to 1 A/cm² current density with low specific energy consumption around 3.3 kWh/Nm³ of produced hydrogen. Elcogen products are unique as their operation temperature is 700 °C in electrolysis mode still being able of utilizing standard industrial materials and manufacturing methods allowing major cost reductions for the technology. This work presents the current status of the electrolyser demonstrator development at Elcogen.

Acknowledgement

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 838014 (C2FUEL).

References

- [1] O. Schmidt, A. Gambhir, I. Staffell, A. Hawkes, J. Nelson, and S. Few, Future cost and performance of water electrolysis: An expert elicitation study, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 42 (52) 28.12.2017, pp. 30470-30492.

Keywords: EFCF 2022, Solid Oxide Technologies, SOC, Fuel Cells, SOFC, Electrolysers, SOE, CO₂ Reuse, C2FUEL, Green hydrogen, Elcogen